

Synthesis, Physico-chemical and antioxidant activity of Cr(III), Fe(II) and Ni(II) Complexes with Schiff base N-2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4-methoxyaniline

Ibrahim A. K.¹

Department of Pure and Industrial Chemistry, Bayero University, Kano, Nigeria

Email: al.ameen91@yahoo.com

Mani, S.

Department of Chemistry Education, Federal College of Education, Technical Gusau, Nigeria

Abstract: The Schiff base (N-2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4-methoxyaniline) derived from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and 4-methoxyaniline and its Cr(III), Fe(II), and Ni(II) metal complexes were synthesized and characterized using infrared spectral analysis, melting point/decomposition temperature, magnetic susceptibility, conductivity measurement, solubility test, and elemental analyses. The Schiff base and its metal complexes were screened for antioxidant activity. The molar conductance values range ($2.70 - 26.2 \Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$) indicated all complexes are nonelectrolytes. The magnetic susceptibility values revealed that Cr(III) and Fe(II) complexes are paramagnetic while Ni(II) complex is diamagnetic. The infrared spectra analysis suggested that the Schiff bases behave as a bidentate ligand coordinates to metal ion via azomethine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen. The high decomposition temperature range ($210 - 242^\circ\text{C}$) indicated the stability of the complexes. The elemental analysis results revealed slight differences between observed and calculated percentages of C, H, and N in all the prepared compounds, this is in conformity with the proposed structures of the compounds. The antioxidant activity of Schiff base and its metal complexes was measured on the basis of the radical scavenging effect of 1,1-diphenyl-2-picryl-hydrazyl (DPPH)-free radical activity. The results revealed that the Schiff base and its metal complexes possessed promising antioxidant activity.

Keywords: Schiff base, Complexes, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, 4-methoxyaniline, Antioxidant activity, DPPH.

Introduction:

The chemistry of (-C=N-) plays a vital role in the progress of chemical and medical science. Schiff bases are characterized by the presence of the azomethine functional group (-C=N-), and are usually formed by condensation of a primary amine with carbonyl compound i.e. aldehyde & Ketone (Iniama and Isaac, 2013). The first reports of this kind of reaction have been published by Hugo Schiff in the 1860s. Thereafter Schiff bases have been intensively used as synthetic intermediates and as Ligands for coordinating transition and inner transition metal ions, (Anita *et al.*, 2010). Schiff bases have been widely used as ligand because of the high stability of their coordination compounds, good solubility in common solvents such as methanol, chloroform, Dimethylsulfoxide, and Dimethylformamide e.t.c (Bharat *et al.*, 2015). Schiff bases obtained from aromatic aldehyde and aromatic amines have shown a number of applications in many fields such as pharmaceutical, life sciences, and chemical science (Muzammil *et al.*, 2015). These important

¹ Corresponding author

compounds have been reported to possess diverse biological activities such as antifungal, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antioxidant, and antitumor, (Neelofar *et al.*, 2017). Metal complexes have been receiving considerable attention for many years, due to their interesting characteristics in the field of material science and a biological system (Rajendra, *et al.*, 2012). Metal complexes have important application in medicinal chemistry, medical science demands such types of compounds which are more potent, biologically active, easily absorbable and nontoxic, and show fast action for the treatment of diseases (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2017). Extensive studies revealed that chelation makes the complex more stable and biologically more active in the presence of bio-metal. Metal ions fixed the complexes at the specific active site of the proteins and enzymes of the host and show their potentiality (Chaudhary, 2013).

Materials and Method:

All chemicals were purchased from Sigma Aldrich and used without further purification. All glassware used were washed with detergent after soaking in conc. HNO₃, rinsed with distilled water and dried in an oven. The weighing was conducted using the electrical Melter balance model AB54. Infrared spectral analysis was determined using Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer (FTIR-8400S) range 4000-400cm⁻¹. Electrical conductance was measured using the Jenway conductivity meter model 4010 range 20-200μs. Melting points and decomposition temperatures were determined using the microprocessor melting point apparatus (WRS-IB). Magnetic susceptibility was determined using magnetic susceptibility balance MKI Sherwood scientific ltd. Elemental analyses were determined using Series II CHNS/O 2400 Perkin Elmer.

Preparation of Schiff base:

The Schiff base was prepared by mixing the ethanolic solution of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde with that of ethanolic solution of 4-methoxyaniline in a 1:1 ratio. The resulting solution was refluxed for 4hours and then cools to room temperature; on cooling the precipitate formed, which was then filtered, washed, and recrystallized with ethanol and diethyl-ether and then dried in desiccators over anhydrous CaCl₂ for 72hrs (Gomathi, *et al.*, 2013).

Preparation metal complexes:

The complexes were prepared by mixing a hot ethanolic solution of hydrated metal chloride salts of Cr(III), Fe(II), and Ni(II) with that of hot ethanolic solution of Schiff base ligand in 1:2 ratios. The resulting mixture was reflux for 8 hrs, in each case, and then cool to room temperature, on cooling the precipitate formed, which was then filtered, washed with ethanol and diethyl-ether several times to remove any excess ligand. And finally dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 in desiccators to obtained required complexes (Gomathi, *et al.*, 2013).

Determination of Melting point of Schiff base and Decomposition Temperature of the metal complexes:

The melting point of the Schiff base and the decomposition temperature of metal complexes were determined using the microprocessor melting point apparatus (WRS-IB). The results obtained are shown in Table 1.

Solubility Test:

The solubility test of Schiff base and its metal complexes were carried out in the water, Diethyl-ether ethanol, methanol, acetone, and chloroform, Dimethylsulfoxide and

Dimethylformamide in which 0.2g of each sample was tested in 10 ml of each solvent. The results obtained are shown in (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2018)

Determination of Water of Hydration in the Complexes:

0.2 g of prepared complex each was placed in a clean weighted Petri dish which was then placed in an oven at 110 °C for 72 hrs until a constant weight was obtained.

The weight loss if any, recorded as the water of hydration from the constant weight of anhydrous complex; the percentage water of hydration was calculated for each complex using the expression below:

$$\% \text{ water of hydration} = \frac{\text{weight loss}}{\text{initial weight of sample}} \times 100\% \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Molar conductance measurements:

1 mmol of each complex was dissolved in 10ml of Dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) and the corresponding specific conductance value was recorded using Jenway conductivity meter model 4010 (Moamens, 2013).

From the specific conductance value recorded, the molar conductance of each metal complex was calculated using the expression below. The results obtained are shown in Table 3.

$$\text{Molar conductance} = \frac{100 \times \text{specific conductance}}{\text{ionic concentration}} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Magnetic Susceptibility Measurement:

The magnetic susceptibility of complexes was determined using magnetic susceptibility balance MKI Sherwood science ltd via the expression below. The results obtained are shown in Table 4 (Javed, 2006).

$$X_g = CL \frac{(R-R_0)}{10^9 M} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where X_g = Mass susceptibility, $C = 1$ (Constant), L = Sample length in the tube (whose range should be set between 1.5 to 3.5cm, R = Reading obtained from the sample packed in the tube, R_0 = Reading obtained from preweight empty tube, M = mass of the sample in the tube (measured in gram).

Antioxidant experiments:

The method used by Saif *et al.*, (2016) was adopted with little modifications. DPPH (8 mg) was dissolved in methanol (300mL). Series dilutions were carried out with stock solutions (4 mmol) of free ligand and its metal complexes in methanol to obtain concentrations of 2.0-0.05 mmol. Diluted solutions (2mL each) were mixed with DPPH (2mL) and allowed to stand for 30 min, for any reaction to occur. The absorbance was recorded at 517nm using a JASCO model V-550 UV-Vis spectrophotometer when the odd electron becomes paired off in the presence of a free radical scavenger, the absorption reduces, and the DPPH solution is decolorized as the color changes from deep violet to light yellow. The degree of reduction in absorbance measurement is indicative of the radical scavenging (antioxidant) activity. The experiment was performed twice and the average absorbance was noted for each concentration of the test compound that reduced

50% of the initial free radical concentration, which was calculated as μmol . Ascorbic acid was used as reference standards. The control sample was prepared to contain the same volume without test and reference compounds. The radical scavenging activity of the tested samples, expressed as percentage inhibition of DPPH, was calculated according to the formula $I(\%) = [(A_0 - A_t)/A_0] \times 100$, where A_t is the absorbance value of the tested sample and A_0 is the absorbance value of the blank sample, in a particular time. The linear regression fitting between the % inhibition and log concentration was determined by probit analysis using IBM SPSS statistic 20.0 software. And the concentration corresponding to 50% inhibition was expressed as IC_{50} value. A lower IC_{50} value indicates greater antioxidants activity.

Results Discussion:

Table 1: Physical and Analytical Data of Schiff base and its metal Complexes

Compound	Color	Mol.Formula	Mol.wt	Melt.pt/Dec Temp. (°C)	%Yield	Elemental analysis Calculate (Found)		
						%C	%H	%N
Schiff base	Yellow	$C_{18}H_{15}NO_2$	277.0	112	68.59	77.98 (74.56)	5.42 (3.93)	5.05 (6.24)
$[CrL_2(H_2O)_2]$	Brown	$C_{36}H_{32}CrN_2O_6$	640.0	210	74.60	67.50 (68.56)	5.00 (3.67)	4.38 (6.07)
$[FeL_2(H_2O)_2]$	Black	$C_{36}H_{32}FeN_2O_6$	643.9	242	69.25	67.10 (68.56)	4.97 (4.39)	4.35 (3.92)
$[NiL_2].4H_2O$	Green	$C_{36}H_{36}NiN_2O_8$	682.7	217	77.28	63.28 (63.89)	5.27 (4.31)	4.10 (3.70)

Key: L = Ligand, Cr = Chromium, Fe = Iron, Ni = Nickel

Table 2: IR Spectra of the Schiff base and metal Complexes

Compound	$V(C=N) \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$V(M-O) \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$V(M-N) \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$V(H_2O) \text{ cm}^{-1}$
Schiff base	1614	-	-	-
$[CrL_2(H_2O)_2]$	1607	602	510	3327
$[FeL_2(H_2O)_2]$	1599	608	513	3566
$[NiL_2].4H_2O$	1599	600	521	3305

Key: L= Ligand, Cr = Chromium, Fe = Iron, Ni = Nickel

Table 3: Conductivity Measurement of Complexes in DMSO

Complex	Concentration	Specific Conductance	Molar Conductance
	Mol dm^{-3}	$\text{Ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\text{Ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
$[CrL_2(H_2O)_2].$	1.0×10^{-3}	12.9×10^{-6}	12.9
$[FeL_2(H_2O)_2]$	1.0×10^{-3}	26.2×10^{-6}	26.2
$[NiL_2].4H_2O$	1.0×10^{-3}	2.70×10^{-6}	2.70

Key: L= Ligand, DMSO= Dimethylsulfoxide, Cr = Chromium, Fe, Iron, Ni = Nickel

Table 4: Magnetic Susceptibility of the Complexes

Compound	Xg(gmol ⁻¹)	Xm(gmol ⁻¹)	μ _{eff} (BM)	Property
[CrL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	9.34×10 ⁻⁶	5.98×10 ⁻³	3.78	Paramagnetic
[FeL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	1.72×10 ⁻⁵	1.11×10 ⁻²	5.15	Paramagnetic
[NiL ₂].4H ₂ O	-1.67×10 ⁻⁷	-1.14×10 ⁻⁴	-Ve	Diamagnetic

Key: L = Ligand, Cr = Chromium, Fe, Iron, Ni = Nickel

Table 6: In vitro DPPH radical scavenging activity of Schiff base and its metal Complexes

Compound	DPPH Scavenging activity
	IC ₅₀ (μmol)
Schiff base	0.496
[CrL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	0.069
[FeL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	0.001
[NiL ₂].4H ₂ O	2.784
Ascorbic Acid (Standard)	0.350

Key: L = Ligand, DPPH = 1, 1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl, Cr = Chromium, Fe = Iron, Ni = Nickel

Discussion:

The reaction between 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and 4-methoxyaniline yielded Schiff base ligand (N-2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4-methoxyaniline) which is yellow solid with a percentage yield of 68.59% and melting point temperature of 112°C. (Table.1) this is in agreement with the color and closer in melting point reported by Dailami *et al.*, (2016).

The reaction between Schiff base and a hydrated metal salt of Cr(III), Fe(II), and Ni(II), formed complexes with different physical properties; such as color and decomposition temperature (Table.1), the colors may be due to charge transfer or nature of the ligand. The decomposition temperature of the Complexes fall in the range of 210°C-242°C respectively (Table.1), these high temperature indicated the good stability of the Complexes due to coordination between the Schiff base and the metal ion and the tremendous nature of the Complexes. Also, the elemental analysis data revealed slight differences between the calculated and observed percentage values of CHN respectively (Table.1). These values are in good agreement with the proposed stoichiometry of the prepared complexes.

The Schiff base and its corresponding metal complexes are soluble in some common organic solvents such as chloroform, Dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) methanol, acetone, and Dimethylformamide (DMF) and insoluble in water and Diethyl-ether.

The values obtained in the spectrum of the Schiff base showed a band at 1614cm⁻¹ which is attributed to V (>C=N-) stretching vibration and this band shifted to lower region range (1599-1607cm⁻¹) in the spectra of the Cr(III), Fe(II) and Ni(II) complexes respectively. (Table.2) indicating the coordination of the Schiff base with the metal ion through the nitrogen atom of the azomethine group and phenolic oxygen. The new bands appeared in the spectra of the complexes in the ranges (600-608cm⁻¹) and (510-521cm⁻¹), these bands are attributed to V(M-O) and V(M-N) stretching vibration respectively, (Table.2) also indicating the coordination of the Schiff base ligand to the metal(II) ion. Another band appeared in the spectra of some of the complexes in the region range (3305-3566cm⁻¹) which may be attributed to V(H₂O) stretching vibration. This is in line with a similar report from previous literature.

Figure 1: IR Spectrum of Schiff base

Figure 2: IR Spectrum of Cr(III) Complex

Figure 3: IR Spectrum of Fe(II) Complex

Figure 4: IR spectrum of Ni(II) complex

The molar conductance values range ($2.7 - 26.2\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$) indicated all the complexes are nonelectrolyte (Table 3). The values obtained are very close to the values reported by Uddin *et al.*, (2014).

The values obtained from magnetic susceptibility measurement of the prepared complexes at room temperature i.e.; 3.78BM and 5.15BM revealed Cr(III) and Fe(II) complexes as paramagnetic while $-Ve$ revealed Ni(II) as diamagnetic (Table 4).

The result obtained from DPPH scavenging activity of Schiff base and the metal complexes shows $IC_{50} = 0.496$ for Schiff base, $IC_{50} = 0.001$ for Fe(II) complex, $IC_{50} = 0.069$ for Cr(III) complex and $IC_{50} = 2.784$ for Ni(II) complex (Table 5), these values indicated promising antioxidant activity of the prepared compounds.

Conclusion:

The Schiff base N-2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4-methoxyaniline and its Cr(III), Fe(II) and Ni(II) complexes were synthesized and characterized successfully. The molar conductance values revealed non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The IR and elemental analysis data revealed 1:2 metal-ligand ratios in all the complexes. All the prepared compounds showed excellent antioxidant activity; among which the Fe(II) and Cr(III) complexes showed higher antioxidant activity than Ascorbic acid (Standard).

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